

Investigation of the Electromagnetic Behavior of Complementary Split-Ring Resonators: Toward a Novel CSRR Design

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Abstract—In this work, we study the behavior of electromagnetic complementary composite periodic media via an approach based on their supported eigenmodes for in-plane wave propagation. The numerical eigen-analysis which is based on the spurious-free field-flux eigenmode finite element formulation proves the need for metal-backing of the structure to support the complementary mode. Parametric analyses are presented for the cases of varying distances between the resonators and the ground plane. We also prove the feasibility of complementary structures to support resonance modes with partial ground termination of metallic strips leading to a novel metamaterial particle presented first time in the literature. Experimental results confirm the numerical simulations and prove its potential for incorporation in more complex microwave planar structures.

Index Terms—Complementary split-ring resonators (SRRs), eigenvalue analysis, in-plane incidence, novel complementary resonator.

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING the past decades, there has been a growing interest in the research field of metamaterials. Artificial structures with exotic electromagnetic properties not readily found in nature are designed, studied, and incorporated in complex circuits in microwave, THz, and optical frequencies [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. The most celebrated metamaterial particle, initially proposed in [6], is the split-ring resonator (SRR), the first composite structure to exhibit negative effective magnetic permeability, through its excitation with an incident magnetic field polarized perpendicular to its plane. Several numerical, analytical, or semi-analytical techniques were used to describe and retrieve its effective electromagnetic parameters, along with the involvement of cross-polarization phenomena producing bianisotropy [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], whereas its implementation and integration inside

RF circuits as an individual particle or as a periodic array also find very popular applications [16]. Moreover, many variations in the initial edge-coupled SRR (EC-SRR) design have been proposed: The broadside-coupled SRR (BC-SRR), the non-bianisotropic SRR (NB-SRR), the 2-cut SRR, the electric ring resonator (ERR), etc. [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22]. In addition, the popular field of metasurfaces—the planar version of metamaterial composites—has also triggered the study of the behavior of the resonators under in-plane or perpendicular wave incidence with respect to their plane: Absorbers, impedance matching surfaces, optical metasurfaces, and tunable and reconfigurable metasurfaces have been recently proposed, incorporating periodic repetitions of resonant particles, or even nonperiodic versions of them, along with several characterization techniques for the extraction of their effective surface susceptibilities [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29].

The creation of negative effective permittivity $\epsilon_{r,\text{eff}}$ at microwave frequency bands was initially achieved by an array of parallel metallic thin wires, under the excitation of an electric field parallel to their axis [30]. This medium behaves as a low-frequency plasma exhibiting a negative real part of $\epsilon_{r,\text{eff}}$ up to an electric plasma frequency, where it turns to a positive value, tending asymptotically to the value of 1. Utilization of the Babinet principle in the design of artificial composites led to the birth of resonant particles, such as the complementary versions of the SRRs, leading to composite media which exhibit negative effective electric permittivity of resonant nature. Substitution of metallic parts with air (or dielectric), and vice versa, produces the dual effect: An incident electric field on a complementary EC-SRR composite medium exhibits complementary properties with respect to the propagation in the corresponding ordinary resonator medium, i.e., a resonance is created at a similar frequency range with the ordinary SRR medium, owing to the excited resonant anti-parallel electric polarizability, leading to the medium's negative effective dielectric permittivity property [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [36], [37]. Incorporation of these complementary resonators in microwave components such as antennas, substrate-integrated waveguides, filters, and sensors has been extensively reported in [38], [39], [40], [41], [42], [43], [44], and [45].

The objective of this work is a thorough study and description of the behavior of composite periodic media consisting

Received 20 September 2024; revised 8 October 2024; accepted 11 October 2024. This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program through the Marie Skłodowska-Curie under Grant 101064186. (Corresponding author: Michalis Nitas.)

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Color versions of one or more figures in this article are available at <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2024.3481330>.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TMTT.2024.3481330

of complementary resonators via a numerical eigenmode approach. Due to the complexity of the structures, there is a need for more accurate approximations, and therefore, a more precise approach is feasible by the utilization of numerical methods. We use our formerly proposed field-flux Bloch–Floquet finite element method (FEM) formulation for periodic structures to gain access to the information of the modes supported by these media, at specified frequency ranges where resonance is exhibited [46], [47], [48]. The returned eigenpairs (i.e., the complex propagation constants and the field distributions of the supported modes) offer a very precise and complete approach on the intrinsic behavior of these structures, with available information about the supported wave type, both at passband and inside bandgap regions. Therefore, evaluating the numerical eigensolutions, we are able to visualize the field mode distributions at arbitrary planes all over their unit cells, obtaining, in this way, an accurate picture of the microscopic field quantities, especially at regions very close to the scatterers. Thus, there is no need to characterize a priori the type of propagating field inside the structures as TEM, TE, TM, or hybrid, assuming the elimination of certain field components, which are numerically proved to be of nonzero magnitude [49]. We note that throughout this work, all the eigensolutions are cross-checked with wave excitation simulations, with orthogonal polarization incidences. The compared results are in perfect agreement with respect to the coincidence of the frequency ranges of the bandgaps (returned from the eigensolutions) and the resonances seen at the transmission coefficients (returned from the wave excitation solutions).

As a first step, the in-plane incidence on a complementary EC-SRR composite medium is considered, where the resonators are not grounded by any metallic pattern. The returned dispersion diagram confirms this medium’s inability to support resonant modes, due to the lack of a ground plane, a feature that proves to be necessary for the formation of anti-parallel electric dipole moments, an effect that renders the medium’s effective relative permittivity negative. Next, the termination of the structure at a metallic ground plane follows, with its returned dispersion diagrams exhibiting a resonant behavior at almost the same frequency ranges with the ordinary EC-SRR media. The duality of the overall behavior is also justified by the visualization of the supported field distributions, where the electric and magnetic field distributions of the supported modes at specific frequencies exhibit dual characteristics when plotted at planes exactly above and below the scatterers.

Subsequently, a parametric analysis is carried out, varying the distance between the scatterers and the ground plane, where it is obvious that the resonance frequency of this structure decreases with the proximity of the ground plane, due to the increase in the capacitance formed between the resonators and the metal-backing. Furthermore, we study the partial metal termination of a complementary EC-SRR particle with a varying width microstrip line and a cross-shaped metallic pattern. The results show that these structures maintain the similarity of the dispersion diagrams and the field distributions of the supported modes. Therefore, it is shown that there is no need for full conductive termination of a complementary medium, to support its resonant mode. Taking this design procedure one

step further, we propose the simplified complementary SRR, a novel resonator particle, by etching the unnecessary metallic parts from the scatterers’ plane, leaving only a conductive ring and the needed conductive connection strips. We prove the presented particle’s capability to support the complementary SRR’s modes, exhibiting an almost identical behavior, with respect to the dispersion diagram and the mode field distributions. Finally, as a proof of concept, we fabricate and measure the periodic repetition of this novel structure and compare the simulations with the experimental results.

II. COMPUTATIONAL AND THEORETICAL FRAME

A. Numerical Approximation

Here we present the numerical tool, used throughout this work for the acquisition of the numerical solution of a periodic structure. We briefly describe the **e-b** finite element periodic formulation, whereas its detailed derivation may be found in [46], [47], [48], and [52]. We also note that all the computational tools were implemented in the weak form of Comsol Multiphysics¹ and verified in custom in-house codes in MATLAB¹, returning identical results when solved for the same number of degrees of freedom. Throughout the work, the time-factor $\exp(j\omega t)$ is assumed and suppressed, with ω being the angular frequency and t being the time.

According to the Bloch–Floquet theorem, the electric field **E** and the magnetic induction **B** may be written as the product of their periodic envelopes **e** and **b**, respectively, and an exponential factor as

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{e} e^{-j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} \quad (1a)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{b} e^{-j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}}, \quad (1b)$$

where $\mathbf{k} = k\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ is the Bloch–Floquet wavevector of the prescribed propagation direction $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ (e.g., $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$) and $k = \beta - j\alpha$ is the unknown complex propagation constant. Substituting (1) into Maxwell’s curl equations in the frequency domain, we obtain the following modified Maxwell’s equations in terms of the periodic field envelopes:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{e} - jk\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} = -j\omega\mathbf{b} \quad (2a)$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} - jk\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} = j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r \mathbf{e}. \quad (2b)$$

Here, $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r$ and $\bar{\bar{\mu}}_r$ are the 3×3 tensors of relative dielectric permittivity and relative magnetic permeability, respectively. Subsequently, we take the Galerkin formulation for this system of equations by projecting the first equation with the test magnetic induction field \mathbf{b}' and the second equation with the test electric field \mathbf{e}' and integrating inside the volume V of the computational domain, enclosed by the surface S as

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{e} \, dV - jk \iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} \, dV \\ = -j\omega \iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \mathbf{b} \, dV \end{aligned} \quad (3a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_V \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{e}' \, dV - jk \iiint_V \mathbf{e}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} \, dV \\ = j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0 \iiint_V \mathbf{e}' \cdot \bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r \mathbf{e} \, dV + \iint_S (\mathbf{e}' \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS, \end{aligned} \quad (3b)$$

¹Trademarked.

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ denotes the outward unitary vector normal to the boundary. Expansion of the electric field \mathbf{e} with tangentially continuous edge-based H -curl elements and magnetic flux density \mathbf{b} with normally continuous facet-based H -div elements together with the application of the appropriate boundary conditions results in the following linear eigenvalue problem

$$\begin{bmatrix} -j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0\mathbf{T}^{E'E} + \mathbf{T}_s^{E'E} & \mathbf{Q}^{E'B} - \mathbf{T}^{E'B} \\ \mathbf{Q}^{B'E} & j\omega\mathbf{T}^{B'B} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} = k \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -j\mathbf{P}^{E'B} \\ -j\mathbf{P}^{B'E} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where the submatrices are defined in [47]. The solution of this matrix eigenvalue problem returns the complex propagation constant as eigenvalue k and the corresponding field distribution as eigenvector for a given frequency, providing numerical information all over the simulated frequency spectrum, at pass-band and at bandgap regions. Regarding the assumptions used in this work, we simulated the conductors with the impedance boundary condition, with a typical copper conductivity $\sigma = 5.88 \times 10^7$ S/m), and terminated the boundaries of the unit cell with periodic boundary conditions (continuity for the Bloch–Floquet periodic envelopes).

B. Babinet Principle and Complementarity

The phenomenon of the creation of a resonant polarizability exhibiting anti-parallel direction with respect to the incident electric field in a complementary EC-SRR medium is well-described in [3], [31], [32], [33], and [34]. We consider a 3D-periodic composite medium consisting of ordinary EC-SRRs, arranged in an orthorhombic grid of edge d , allowing in-plane incidence of the electromagnetic wave k_x or k_y (the unit cell of a typical resonator medium is shown in Fig. 1). The response of such a medium under an incident wave polarized as (E_y, H_z, k_x) is well-described in the literature: The splits on each of the rings force the electric current to flow across the slots between them, acting as a displacement current and rendering the slots as a distributed capacitance. Thus, an anti-parallel magnetic dipole moment m_z of resonant form is created at a specific frequency zone around a resonant frequency ω_0 .

According to the Babinet principle and under the assumption that there is no dielectric substrate involved and the metallic parts are infinitely thin and lossless, the behavior for the complementary EC-SRR particle is expected to be exactly the dual one: The response of a complementary EC-SRR composite periodic medium under a wave polarized as $(E_z, -H_y, k_x)$ is expected to consist of an anti-parallel resonant electric dipole moment at the same frequency zone with the EC-SRR's magnetic moment previously described, with the complementary effective medium exhibiting an effective electric permittivity ($\epsilon_{r,z}$) of resonant form. It is also noted that the omega-type bianisotropic behavior exhibited by the ordinary SRR should also be considered and extended to its complementary counterpart [3]. A very important issue that becomes more obvious in the context of this work is that the creation of an electric dipole moment requires the

Fig. 1. (a) Unit cell of a complementary EC-SRR composite medium (non metal-backed). (b) Detailed dimensions of the EC-SRR particle in mm.

presence of a conducting plane at some distance from the resonators, acting as a ground plane, in a way that the dipole moments (anti-parallel with respect to the incident wave) are formed, perpendicular to the direction of the in-plane wave incidence. In the next section, the qualitative proof of the aforementioned statements is given by the visualization of the field distributions of the supported eigenmodes of a complementary EC-SRR medium returned by the numerical solution of the considered eigenproblem.

III. NUMERICAL APPROACH ON THE COMPLEMENTARY RESONATORS

A. Need for Metal-Backing

Initially, we explore the behavior of a resonator medium, which is not metal-backed, as shown in Fig. 1. The composite medium comprises of complementary EC-SRRs periodically assembled in a cubic orthorhombic grid of edge $d_x = d_y = d_z = 10$ mm, whereas the incident wave is assumed to illuminate the structure with a wavevector parallel to the x -axis (k_x incidence). The dispersion diagram of the aforementioned structure is presented in Fig. 2(a): It is obvious that there are no resonant modes supported by this composite medium, whereas the only mode appearing inside the irreducible Brillouin zone at every frequency is the lightline mode, the E_z component of which is illustrated in Fig. 2(b) at a few xy planes (a TEM wave, as thoroughly explained in [49]). We may conclude that the absence of resonant modes is justified by the absence of metal-backing, exhibiting the inability of this structure to create dipole moments directed along the z -axis.

In addition, a parametric analysis of the z -stacking parameter d_z was performed, to assess its behavior versus the proximity of the resonators at the z -direction. The results configure the same behavior of the medium, with respect to the supported modes, returning identical dispersion diagrams (not shown). Finally, the case of k_y incidence was studied, as well, which returned identical results in terms of the dispersion diagrams and the mode distributions compared with those returned from k_x incidence (i.e. no other (resonant) modes were returned from the solution of the eigenproblem, except for the lightline modes). At this point, we point out that we discriminate our analysis with respect to the perpendicular wave incidence case at a non metal-backed complementary

Fig. 2. (a) Dispersion diagram of a non metal-backed complementary EC-SRR medium. The only returned modes are the lightline ones, a proof that this specific medium is not capable of supporting any resonant modes. (b) Plot of the E_z component of the lightline mode at 5 GHz.

Fig. 3. (a) Metal-backed complementary EC-SRR resonator. The ground plane is placed at a distance of d_{pcb} , whereas the volume in between is filled with a dielectric substrate. (b) Microstrip-backed complementary EC-SRR unit cell. The medium is partially terminated at a microstrip line of width w_m placed at a distance of d_{pcb} .

resonator [34], [51]. This case is thoroughly examined in [51] both as an eigenvalue and as an excitation problem, where the supported modes creating the bandpass frequency range are fully described and justified.

B. Eigenmode Analysis Approach for Metal-Backed Resonator Medium

Subsequently, we study the behavior of the grounded complementary EC-SRR composite medium (Fig. 3). Under the assumption that the metallization covers all the ground plane of the unit cell, placed at a distance of $d_{pcb} = 1.6$ mm and the dielectric substrate is air ($\epsilon_r = 1$), we extract the dispersion diagram of this medium for k_x incidence, as shown in Fig. 4. It is obvious that the complementary EC-SRR mode appears on the dispersion diagram, forming the classical two-branch dispersion scheme, exhibiting a bandgap frequency region of 1 GHz (5.3–6.3 GHz), whereas the lightline modes still exist, forming the straight line on the diagram with a slope of $c_0/2\pi$. In comparison to the dispersion diagram of an ordinary EC-SRR composite medium presented in [49], we may easily observe the similarities between them and conclude that in the case of the complementary EC-SRR medium (terminated with metallic ground at a distance of $d_{pcb} = 1.6$ mm), the appearing bandgap region is 30% larger compared with that of the ordinary EC-SRR medium (5.3–6 GHz for the latter case). We note, of course, that the resonant behavior of the EC-SRR medium is due to the

Fig. 4. Dispersion diagram for k_x incidence of a fully metal-backed complementary EC-SRR medium with $d_{pcb} = 1.6$ mm. The resonant mode is visible, forming a two-branch curve separated by a bandgap region of 1 GHz at 5.3–6.3 GHz. Lightline modes are returned, as well, forming the straight (light) line. The eigenvalues with large propagation and attenuation constants are shown in green, those with very small (tend to zero) propagation constant and large attenuation constant are plotted in red, and those which form the branches of the modes (passband) are depicted in blue. Lightline modes are plotted in black, lightline plotted with a continuous black line.

Fig. 5. (a) Normal magnetic field distribution H_z exactly above the resonators' surface for the supported resonant mode of the metal-backed complementary EC-SRR medium at 5 GHz. The mode distribution below the resonator is identical (not shown). (b) Normal electric field distribution E_z of the same mode exactly below and above the resonator—a sign change is visible.

creation of negative effective permeability $\mu_{r_{zz,eff}}$, whereas the complementary EC-SRR medium owes its resonant behavior to the creation of negative effective permittivity $\epsilon_{r_{zz,eff}}$.

The field distribution of the normal magnetic field component (H_z) exactly above the resonator plane corresponding to complementary EC-SRR mode at 5 GHz is shown in Fig. 5(a). This field profile is identical to the E_z profile of the corresponding mode of the (ordinary) EC-SRR medium at the same frequency, confirming the property of complementarity of the supported modes by the two media under comparison. The main difference in this case is that there is no sign change on the H_z component distribution below and above the resonator for the complementary EC-SRR. Whereas there is a sign change for the E_z component of the corresponding supported mode for the EC-SRR medium and implies the existence of surface charges microscopically, according to the boundary conditions for the normal components of the dielectric displacement. On the other hand, the plot of the normal electric field component E_z for the same mode for the complementary EC-SRR shown in Fig. 5(b) exhibits a sign change, indeed, confirming the existence of surface charges in this case, as well. Finally, the field distribution of the tangential magnetic field components at the same planes (H_x and H_y) are given in Fig. 6, the sign change of which

Fig. 6. Tangential magnetic field distribution H_x (a) and H_y (b) exactly above and below the resonators' surface for the supported resonant mode of the metal-backed complementary EC-SRR medium at 5 GHz.

Fig. 7. (a) Normal electric field distribution E_z exactly above and below the resonators' surface and the ground plane's surface for the supported resonant mode of the metal-backed complementary EC-SRR medium at 5 GHz. The difference between the upper and lower distributions may be seen as the charge accumulation on them, forming a distributed capacitance on the z -axis, whereas the uniplanar capacitance on the resonator is canceled due to the equal capacities formed at upper and lower half resonators. (b) Schematic to illustrate the accumulation of charges on the resonator's surface.

reveals the macroscopic existence of surface currents on the resonators, as discussed thoroughly in [49].

Fig. 7(a) illustrates the E_z component exactly above and below the resonators' surface [the same plot as in Fig. 5(b)], but plotted along with the E_z distribution at ground surfaces (at both its sides). Taking the difference in the normal component of the dielectric displacement (electric field in this case, as surrounding medium is air, with $\epsilon_r = 1$) on these surfaces as an analog to the charge distribution formed on them, we may conclude that the only capacitance formed is the one between the resonator and the ground plane, leading to the electric resonance form of this particle and the aforementioned negative electric dipole moment. Whereas there is no net capacitance formed on the xy layer, as the upper half capacitance and the lower half capacitance cancel each other, as illustrated in Fig. 7(b), which is provided for a better visual explanation of the charge distribution.

A conclusion that may be extracted by the presented results is the numerical confirmation of the complementarity of the EC-SRR and the metal-backed complementary EC-SRR composite media at in-plane incidence. The similarity of the dispersion diagrams and the duality of the field distributions in the proximity of the scatterers inside the unit cell prove the complementary behavior of the two composite media numerically for the case of in-plane propagation, confirming the

Fig. 8. Dispersion diagrams of fully metal-backed complementary EC-SRR media, varying the distance d_{pcb} between the resonators and the ground plane. A reduction in the resonant frequency is observed along with the reduction in the distance, as the bandgap positions shift down in frequency.

Babinet principle. As a final comment, we note that the mode profiles of the supported modes inside the bandgap region exhibit the same field distributions with the ones depicted in this section at passband frequencies, whereas their attenuation constants are very large, rendering the modes extremely evanescent. Finally, as in the case of an ordinary EC-SRR medium, k_y incidence returns an almost identical dispersion diagram compared with k_x incidence for the complementary medium, as well.

C. Variation in the Distance Between Resonator and Ground Plane—Parametric Analysis and Wave Excitation Confirmation

Here, we present the results of the parametric analysis, with distance d_{pcb} between the resonator and the ground plane as a parameter and assess its impact on the behavior of the complementary EC-SRR medium, in terms of its dispersion diagrams and the profiles of its supported modes. The composite medium has the same dimensions with the one presented in the previous section, while the parameter d_{pcb} varies between 0.4 and 1.6 mm, at typical values of dielectric substrates. The dispersion diagrams returned by this parametric eigen-analysis are summarized in Fig. 8. It is easily concluded that the reduction in the distance between the resonator and the ground plane reduces the resonant frequency of the composite medium, as expected, if one observes the variation in the position of the bandgap zone in frequency. The former conclusion may be confirmed in terms of a circuitual approach, bearing in mind that the resonant frequency of the equivalent circuit is reduced due to the increase in the distributed capacitance owing to the increasing proximity of the charge distributions formed between the resonators and the ground plane. Furthermore, the modes supported by the media under study retain their field characteristics, as easily observed by comparing their field distributions, which are identical to the case of $d_{pcb} = 1.6$ mm presented in the previous section (not shown), thus there is no reason to reproduce them.

As a final step in this parametric analysis, aiming to confirm the behavior of the composite media arising out from the eigenmode analysis, we perform a wave propagation (excitation) finite element simulation in Comsol Multiphysics. The results of this excitation problem are depicted in Fig. 9. We may see that the transmission coefficients S_{21} really follow

Fig. 9. Wave propagation results for the fully metal-backed complementary EC-SRR composite medium of varying distance d_{pcb} , assuming an incident wave of $(E_z, -H_y, k_x)$ for the excitation of electric resonance. The transmission coefficients coincide with the bandgaps of the dispersion diagrams of the corresponding media in Fig. 8 confirming the correct positions of the resonances at the frequency spectrum.

the behavior exhibited by the dispersion diagrams in very good agreement: Assuming an incident wave polarized as $(E_z, -H_y, k_x)$, the resonances are observed at approximately the same positions predicted by the dispersion diagrams of Fig. 8, i.e., they almost coincide with the corresponding bandgap regions on the dispersion diagrams. In addition, it is very useful to note that the modes excited by the medium are absolutely identical with the ones illustrated in the previous subsection (not shown in the case of wave propagation problem) confirming the allover correctness of the reasoning on which the modal analysis and the analytical results were based, that is the excitation of the electric resonance of the complementary EC-SRR medium.

D. Effect of Metal-Backing Width

Up to this point, it has been shown that a necessary condition for the resonance of the complementary EC-SRR medium is the termination of the structure at a metallic ground plane, for the purpose of the formation of electric dipole moment between the resonators and the ground plane. Thus, a question arises whether the partial termination of the resonator at a conducting plane affects its function and—as a result—the modes supported by the composed periodic medium. Therefore, at this point, we present the results of a complementary EC-SRR medium, terminated at a distance of $d_{pcb} = 1.6$ mm with a microstrip of width w_m at the ground plane, with its value varying between 1 and 8 mm [see Fig. 3(b)].

Assuming k_x incidence, the returned dispersion diagrams are summarized in Fig. 10. We may observe that the dispersion behavior of the simulated composite media is almost identical, with a slight reduction in the bandgap's bandwidth along with the decrease in the microstrip width: A microstrip width of $w_m = 8$ mm (most of the ground plane covered by metal) exhibits a 1-GHz bandgap at 5.3–6.3 GHz, whereas in the case of $w_m = 1$ mm, the bandgap bandwidth is decreased to 0.8 GHz (5.5–6.3 GHz).

In Fig. 11, the normal magnetic field component H_z is illustrated at a xy plane exactly above the scatterers for all four cases of the simulated media with varying w_m at 5 GHz. It is very easily concluded that the field distributions are

Fig. 10. Dispersion diagrams of a microstrip-backed complementary EC-SRR medium, with microstrip width w_m varying from 8 to 1 mm. The bandgap position at frequency of the simulated media is almost unaffected toward the reduction in the microstrip width, whereas a slight reduction at their bandwidth range is visible.

Fig. 11. Normal magnetic component H_z of the supported mode of a microstrip-backed complementary EC-SRR medium at 5 GHz exactly above the resonators' plane, for varying microstrip widths w_m . The mode distribution remains unchanged at all the termination cases.

exactly the same for all the cases, something which reveals that the supported mode retains its characteristics, regardless of the width of the microstrip terminated at ground plane. Therefore, we may conclude that the overall resonant behavior of the structure is maintained, confirmed both by the almost unchanged dispersion diagrams and by the existence of the supported modes maintaining the same characteristics and prove the correctness of the next statement: For the existence of a resonant mode supported by a complementary EC-SRR medium, a partial termination of the unit cell suffices for the creation of an identical mode with respect to the full metal termination case. This conclusion may be useful in applications where reduction in conductor losses in wave propagation (not attenuation) at in plane incidence is considered. In addition, we note that the simulated results (not shown here) where the microstrip was interrupted in the propagation direction show that the complementary EC-SRR modes vanish, proving the necessity for electrical continuity between the unit cell components' ground plane at the direction of propagation (k_x incidence in this case).

Finally, the results of a wave propagation simulation are presented in this case, as well, to confirm the aforementioned eigenmode analysis' findings: The S_{21} parameters of a 3D-periodic medium are illustrated in Fig. 12. It is easily concluded that the behavior of the structure remains practically

Fig. 12. Wave propagation results for microstrip-backed complementary EC-SRR medium under $(E_z, -H_y, k_x)$ excitation for varying microstrip widths w_m . The resonance positions at frequency coincide with the corresponding bandgap positions of the dispersion diagram of Fig. 10.

Fig. 13. Dispersion diagrams of a cross-terminated complementary EC-SRR medium, k_x incidence, with microstrip width w_m varying from 8 to 1 mm. The bandgap position at frequency of the simulated media is almost unaffected toward the reduction in the microstrip width, whereas a slight reduction at their bandwidth range is visible.

unchanged under the variance of parameter w_m , with the resonances occurring at exactly the same frequency positions as these of the presence of the bandgaps in Fig. 10.

E. Cross-Terminated Complementary EC-SRR Particle

At this point, we study the behavior of a complementary EC-SRR composite medium, terminated by a cross-shaped metallic pattern. This medium has the advantages of partial metal termination, along with the possibility of illumination by either the k_x or k_y directions. The dispersion diagrams corresponding to k_x incidence, with a varying cross strip width w_m (and a distance of $d_{pcb} = 0.8$ mm), are depicted in Fig. 13, whereas the ones for k_y incidence are illustrated in Fig. 14. It is easily observed that the results exhibit almost identical behavior for both the incidences, rendering the integration of the presented metamaterial in complex microwave circuits indifferent of its positioning.

In Fig. 15, the H_z component is illustrated exactly above the resonators' plane for four different cross widths (1, 2, 4, and 8 mm). The mode supported by all four configurations retains its characteristics, which are identical to the full-metal termination case. In addition, the transmission coefficients of a full periodic cross-terminated EC-SRR medium are depicted in Fig. 16, as extracted from the corresponding excitation problem solution. The transmission minima coincide with the bandwidth positions in frequency in all the termination cases.

Fig. 14. Dispersion diagrams of a cross-terminated complementary EC-SRR medium k_y incidence with microstrip width w_m varying from 8 to 1 mm. The diagram is almost identical to the k_x case.

Fig. 15. Normal magnetic component H_z of the supported mode of a cross-terminated complementary EC-SRR medium at 5 GHz exactly above the resonators' plane, for varying microstrip widths w_m . The mode distribution remains unchanged at all the termination cases.

Fig. 16. Wave propagation results for cross-terminated complementary EC-SRR medium under $(E_z, -H_y, k_x)$ excitation for varying microstrip widths w_m . The resonance positions at frequency coincide with the corresponding bandgap positions of the dispersion diagram of Fig. 13.

IV. NOVEL METAMATERIAL DESIGN

A. Simplified Complementary EC-SRR Particle

Here, we present a novel, simplified design of a complementary EC-SRR particle, which may substitute the bulky version of the initially proposed particle. Except for the partial metal termination proposed in the previous subsections, a more interesting alteration is proposed, concerning the scatterer's plane: A conducting circular ring is left around the complementary resonator, whereas the rest of the (upper) conducting sheet is

Fig. 17. Design of the simplified complementary EC-SRR. A conducting ring of radius 4 mm surrounds the complementary structure (its dimensions are given in Fig. 1), whereas the particle connects to its neighboring elements with strips of width w_m . The rest of the metallic upper plane is etched.

now etched, letting the four cross strips connect each unit cell with its neighboring ones. The proposed particle is illustrated in Fig. 17. It is proved that to support the complementary mode, the particle should exhibit electrical continuity with respect to the propagation direction. This means that every single particle must be connected to its neighboring particles via a metallic strip—its width does not play any significant role, as shown later—so as the anti-parallel effective electric polarizability is formed and maintained across the whole composite medium. If the conductive connection between the particles is lost, the fundamental mode is not supported anymore and the electric polarizability is no longer formed inside the composite medium. We prove this metamaterial composite's capability of supporting the fundamental mode of a complementary EC-SRR (fully metal-backed), exhibiting identical behavior in frequency, as shown by the returned eigen-analysis and excitation problem results.

The dispersion diagram of the proposed medium is depicted in Fig. 18 for the case of k_x incidence, with a microstrip width varying from 2 to 0.1 mm (equal strip widths for upper and lower planes). We may observe the almost identical behavior of the medium, independent of the microstrip width. In comparison to the dispersion diagrams of the fully metal-backed complementary EC-SRR of Fig. 10, the behavior of the supported modes is identical. In addition, the field distribution of the normal magnetic field component above the scatterers is illustrated in Fig. 19. It is easily observed that the supported mode is maintained the same, independent of the strip width, and is identical to the classical complementary SRR. The transmission coefficients of the proposed medium are depicted in Fig. 20, as a returned result of the corresponding excitation problem. The place of the transmission minima absolutely coincides with the bandgaps of the dispersion diagram of

Fig. 18. Dispersion diagrams of the simplified complementary EC-SRR medium, k_x incidence, with microstrip width (upper and lower planes) w_m varying from 2 to 0.1 mm. The bandgap position at frequency of the simulated media is almost unaffected toward the reduction in the microstrip width, whereas a slight reduction at their bandwidth range is visible.

Fig. 19. Normal magnetic component H_z of the supported mode of the simplified complementary EC-SRR medium at 5 GHz exactly above the resonators' plane, for varying microstrip widths w_m . The mode distribution remains unaffected at all the termination cases.

Fig. 20. Wave propagation results for the simplified complementary EC-SRR medium under $(E_z, -H_y, k_x)$ excitation for varying microstrip widths w_m . The resonance positions at frequency coincide with the corresponding bandgap positions of the dispersion diagram of Fig. 18.

Fig. 13. We finally note that the results for the orthogonal (k_y) case (dispersion diagrams and wave propagation simulations) are almost identical with the k_x case.

B. Experimental Results

To verify our theoretical and numerical approach, we have experimentally tested the novel metamaterial medium. To this end, we fabricated a structure consisting of $7 \times 7 \times 7$ unit cells, with the resonators printed on a PCB of dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 2.18$ and a thickness of 0.8 mm (Fig. 21). The whole structure was vertically separated with Rohacell

Fig. 21. Upper (left) and lower (right) printed patterns consisting of seven unit cells of the simplified complementary resonator illustrated in Fig. 17.

Fig. 22. Experimental and simulated transmission for the medium of Fig. 17. A deep is observed at frequencies around 3.5 and 4.5 GHz, indicating the presence of a bandgap.

dielectric of 1-cm thickness and was measured as a two-port network with a vector network analyzer. The measured transmission coefficient is illustrated in Fig. 22, along with the corresponding simulated result. A very good agreement is observed, revealing a dip in the transmission at approximately 3.5–4.5 GHz, confirming the corresponding dispersion diagram for this structure which exhibits a bandgap exactly at this frequency range (not shown).

V. CONCLUSION

This work is a complete study of the behavior of periodic composite media consisting of complementary SRRs. A rigorous full-wave eigenmode analysis is followed using the FEM **E**–**B** Bloch–Floquet formulation to acquire the dispersion diagrams and the field distributions of the supported modes and reveal the mechanisms of interaction between the resonators and the electromagnetic field. It is proved that for in-plane incidence, the metal-backing of the resonators is crucial for the appearance of the supported modes, which possess the dual characteristics compared with those supported by ordinary SRR media. Different conductive termination patterns are proposed, where it is proved that only partial microstrip backing suffices for the support of the initial complementary resonator mode. In addition, a novel particle is proposed, the simplified EC-SRR particle, with its simulated and measured properties proving its capability of supporting complementary modes with minimized conductor presence. Further characterization of the proposed composite media in terms of their effective parameters and their possible involvement into microwave and mm-wave applications will be examined in a future work.

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